

Parenting styles and academic anxiety towards academic performance of grade 11 students

Sherilyn Ann A. Ambion

Abstract

A well-established predictor of academic performance is academic anxiety. High levels of anxiety prevent students from performing to the best of their abilities. The goal of this study was to assess the degree of academic anxiety among Grade 11 students, its effects on their academic performance, and the potential influence of parenting styles employed by their guardians. Respondents were recruited from a private school in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. Out of 167 people who were given the e-survey, a total of 120 (71.86%) responses were gathered from students, while 35 (20.96%) were from parents. The sample consisted of 58 male students (48.3%) and 62 female students (51.7%). The mean age of the sample was 16.45 years (SD = 0.62 years). In terms of a guardian's parenting style, the majority, or 32 out of 35 guardians (91.43%), employ a democratic parenting style, while only 3 (8.57%) and 0 (0%) employ autocratic and permissive parenting styles, respectively. The online survey consisted of a profile checklist together with pre-validated instruments, including a researcher-made questionnaire for academic anxiety and Parenting Style Test adapted from Robinson et al. (1995). The results of comparative analyses revealed that academic anxiety among female students is significantly higher compared with their male counterparts. Moreover, students who scored low in academic anxiety are found to have better academic performances compared with those who have high academic anxiety. On the other hand, the impact of guardians' parenting styles on academic performance was not established. The researcher recommends further studies on similar variables with a higher number of respondents.

Keywords: Academic anxiety; academic performance; family structure; parenting styles.

Sherilyn Ann A. Ambion*

Senior High School Department, Statefields School, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

E-mail: ambionsherilyn@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

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Introduction

One of the most common mental health conditions among students is anxiety, which also affects 33.7% of people globally and has a significant negative influence on academic performance (Vytal et al., 2013; Bandelow & Michaelis, 2015). According to Hashempour and Mehrad (2014), anxiety has a detrimental impact on students by affecting their working memory and resulting in poor academic performance. Given this, researching how academic anxiety affects cognitive performance seems essential to academic success.

As cited in Vitasari et al. (2010), Spielberger defined anxiety as a state of mind marked by tension, worry, uneasiness, and concern brought on by the arousal of the autonomic nervous system. High levels of anxiety can be harmful to one's physical and emotional well-being and negatively affect one's interpersonal, professional, and academic growth (Mirawdali et al., 2018), even if an ideal amount of anxiety is thought to be a drive for high success (Singh, 2015). Overly anxious students may really have difficulties with their academic work.

In their study, Mirawdali et al. (2018) mentioned that during tests, exams, or evaluations, students may suddenly develop anxiety-related impairments. Researchers found that anxious students struggle to avoid distractions and take longer to switch their focus between activities, which has a detrimental impact on their ability to learn, read, write, and memorize. Numerous studies have discovered that anxiety might make it more difficult for individuals to take in, process, and remember information. Working memory can be negatively impacted by this, which will lead to poor cognitive function and accomplishment (Hashempour & Mehrad, 2014).

Additionally, the importance of parental styles and their impact on adolescents' behavior are emphasized in the research. Parenting practices are one of several variables that affect students' academic success. There is, however, a lack of systematic and thorough study on the association between parenting styles and academic achievement, particularly in the Philippines.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework on the impact of academic anxiety and parenting styles towards academic performance of Grade 11 students

Statement of the Problem

The primary goal of this study was to examine whether the parenting style of their guardian and the level of their academic anxiety are factors that impact their academic performance. Moreover, this study specifically seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the students in terms of their level of academic anxiety as to the following:
 - 1.1. Low
 - 1.2. Moderate
 - 1.3. High
2. What is the socio demographic profile of the guardians in terms of their parenting styles as to the following:
 - 2.1. autocratic
 - 2.2. democratic
 - 2.3. permissive
3. Is there a significant difference between students' academic anxiety in terms of:
 - 3.1. gender
 - 3.2. family structure
4. Does parenting style significantly affect students' academic performance?
5. Does academic anxiety significantly affect students' academic performance?

The null hypotheses of this study are:

HO1: There is no significant difference between the academic anxiety of male and female students.

HO2: Parenting styles have no significant effect on the academic performance of the students.

HO3: Students' academic anxiety has no significant effect on their academic performance.

Literature Review

Academic Anxiety

Anxiety is defined as "anticipation, tension, or unease accompanied by fear, dread, or unease towards anything, the source of which is mostly unknown or unacknowledged by the person." It could include ongoing anxiety about the future as well as intense emotional reactions to any choice or decision (Good & Kleinman, 2019; Shakir, 2014). One of the most common emotions is anxiety, which is among the most fundamental components of all human conduct. It is an unpleasant sensation of dread, anxiety, worry, or concern (Barlow et al., 2002). Most researchers concur that having academic anxiety is not necessarily detrimental. According to Hadwin et al. (2009), DordiNejad et al. (2011), and Kahan (2012), people can preserve their motivation and sense of responsibility while also living more responsibly and prosperously with a reasonable amount of anxiety.

Most individuals would not be motivated to do anything in life without anxiety. To encourage students to study for exams and may be inclined, a moderate sense of academic anxiety is required for better results from them. High levels of anxiety have been found to hinder with one's ability to concentrate and have an impact on memory. Thus, one of the obstacles to academic success may be high academic anxiety.

If we care about kids' achievement, one must disregard academic anxiety at all costs. It can lead to serious effects if it is not appropriately treated, including procrastination, poor academic performance, and withdrawal from peer socialization, and other circumstances (Mahato & Jangir, 2012).

Parenting Styles

Parenting style, according to Darling and Steinberg (1993), is a combination of views toward the child that the child picks up on that, when combined, produces an emotional environment where the parental actions are shown. Parenting approach is a quality, a characteristic of the child's social surroundings and, hence, of the parent; it is independent of the developing person's traits.

Baumrind (1978) provided three parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. The strict parenting approach, when parents value a commanding posture and constrained traits logically, focuses more on rewards than punishments. This parenting approach emphasizes strong parental involvement and readiness to comprehend the child's point of view, giving the justification for the child's needs a high priority and imposing restrictions. Parents encourage the development of conversations and explain the reasoning behind their actions and viewpoints to their offspring. This parenting approach results in children who have high social and cognitive skills (Baumrind, 1978). Parents with an authoritarian parenting style are restrictive, controlling, and more likely to employ punishment than praise. Parents who are more authoritarian tend to treat their kids more like property. Children are required to adhere to a rigid set of criteria. Their lack of warmth and affection is noticed (Furnham & Cheng, 2000). Low self-reliance, responsibility, and accomplishment motivation have been linked to this parenting approach (Baumrind, 1978; Furnham & Cheng, 2000). Parents who place few demands on their kids and set loose rules for behavior are said to have a permissive parenting style. In this approach, parents see themselves more as an asset for their children than as active or important figures in charge of planning or influencing the child's present-day or future conduct (Macmull & Ashkenazi, 2019). Children of permissive parents typically lack social responsibility and independence, have poor impulse control, and lack self-reliance (Baumrind, 1978; Dornbusch et al., 1987; Chen et al., 2000).

Parenting Styles and Academic Performance

Given its importance to parent-child connection and its influence on children's development, parenting style has captured the interest of many studies (Ballash et al., 2006; Bögels & Brechman-Toussaint, 2006; McLeod et al., 2007). Numerous studies have linked family factors like excessive control, excessive protection, negativity, non-response, and rejection to anxiety (Letcher et al., 2012; Mellon & Moutavelis, 2011). Intense parental surveillance and intrusion, excessive restriction of their children's activities and/or practices, and a hindrance to independent problem-solving are all characteristics of parents of anxious children. Parents are also excessively concerned and over-protective (McLean, 2020). Anxiety is linked to a reduction in parental supervision and consistent discipline (Jafari et al., 2016).

Research by Dornbusch et al. (1987) found that parenting customs vary by culture. For instance, in European American teenagers, an authoritative parenting style was linked to greater academic performance and school grades. An authoritarian parenting style resulted in lower academic grades, although it was unrelated to academic achievement.

Adolescent academic achievement is associated with psychopathology, delinquency, educational and professional success, and substance abuse, according to research (McDermott et al., 2009; Wiesner & Silbereisen, 2003). The literature recommends assessing college students' academic performance using non-cognitive models that take into consideration variables including colleges and universities, parenting styles, connections between learners and other students, educators, motivation, and academic self-efficacy (Fulton & Turner, 2008; Buckner & Turner, 2009).

In contrast to the Western world, Asia has produced very few studies on the relationship between parenting style and academic achievement (Fulton & Turner, 2008; Buckner & Turner, 2009). In Pakistan, Jabeen et al. (2013) looked into different parenting approaches as predictors of graduates' emotional well-being, the connection between cultural capital and academic accomplishment, and, respectively, psychological well-being.

According to studies by McBride-Chang and Chang (1998) and Winter and Yaffe (2000), the tasks, successes, and academic success of children are significantly influenced by the parenting techniques employed by their parents. Despite the fact that more and more studies demonstrate that better parenting practices affect academic performance, these findings vary depending on the socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and culture of the participants (Spera, 2005).

Studies have examined at the relationship between various parenting practices and approaches and resulted in findings that became well-known in parenting literature (Baumrind, 1971; Darling and Steinberg, 1993). These studies show that the socioeconomic position, ethnicity, and varied cultural origins of parents have a significant impact on parenting practices and academic achievement (Steinberg et al., 1992). Therefore, further study is needed to determine how parental actions affect the academic tasks, competencies, and outcomes of adolescent students. Chemers et al. (2001) claim that a key predictor of academic success is self-efficacy. In addition to some cognitive and non-cognitive factors, Rivers et al. (2012) assert that self-efficacy and other personality factors have an impact on academic success results. This study examined the parenting styles prevalent in Pakistan and the influence of personal traits on academic achievement. This study contributes to the information that would be beneficial to educators as well as parents by examining the mediated effect of self-efficacy on the relationship between prediction factors and the end variable.

Academic Anxiety and Academic Achievement

Researchers have been investigating how anxiety affects children's academic achievement, and they have found that high school pupils who claim to have greater levels of anxiety have worse academic results (Mazzone et al., 2007). Students who experience significant levels of anxiety are unable to focus, pay attention for longer periods of time, and maintain their composure.

Students often feel wrath and regret while they are experiencing worry in difficult study-related situations. In general, low performance and elevated levels of worry were more significantly associated in low ability students (Sena et al., 2007). The end-of-semester exam results show that students who are more stressed typically do worse (Hamzah, 2007). Others such as Mazzone et al. (2007) and Sena et al., (2007) expressed that the high levels of worry would result in subpar academic performance. According to the research, anxiety and academic achievement are highly associated (El-Anzi, 2005), and high academic achievement is favorably correlated with less anxiety and less fear.

One of the many factors that can hinder students' academic progress is academic anxiety. It has been shown that students with high levels of academic anxiety behave differently from those with low levels. Parvez and Shakir (2014) looked at high exam anxiety as one of the main factors contributing to university students' subpar performance. Sharma and Sud (1990) found that test anxiety is more prevalent in female students than in male students. Lewinsohn et al. (1998) as cited in Barlow (2000) found that girls were twice as probable as boys to suffer anxiety problems as they turn six years old.

Hancock (2001) found that anxious children performed badly and lacked motivation to learn. Pomerantz et al. (2002) looked at the relationship between internal discomfort and gender inequalities in academic achievement. While girls outperform boys in every topic, they were more prone to experiencing internal conflict. Academic success and anxiety are inversely correlated, according to Singh and Thukral (2009). Rezazadeh and Tavakoli (2009) observed that there is a statistically significant inverse relationship between test anxiety and academic performance. They also found that female students experience test anxiety at a higher rate than male students.

High levels of anxiety are significantly correlated with poor academic performance, according to Weda and Sakti (2018). According to DordiNejal et al. (2011) as cited in Wangdi (2019), test anxiety has a detrimental impact on students' academic performance. Academic anxiety was found to be inversely connected with academic achievement, according to Jain (2012), and there was no discernible difference between boys' and girls' academic anxiety.

According to the findings of Ali et al. (2013), test anxiety was negatively correlated with students' performance in the subject of English, and test anxiety was higher in female students than in male students. Ali et al. (2013) said that test anxiety significantly decreased students' overall accomplishment scores in all four science subjects—physics, chemistry, biology, and mathematics. Low achievement scores were a result of high test anxiety. According to Sridevi (2013), there is an inverse association between general anxiety disorder and academic achievement, as well as a low correlation between the two.

Numerous studies have discovered that adolescents who are more anxious at school perform worse academically (Rana & Mahmood, 2010; Hamzah, 2007; Sena et al., 2007). There is a link between academic worry and poor academic performance (Ali et al., 2013; Peleg, 2009). Although there are more male than female readers, it is interesting to note that female students consistently outperform male students in practically all academic examinations.

This is the result of a variety of elements, including intelligence, study habits, creativity, aptitude, interests, and socioeconomic factors, and cannot be assigned to a single component. Along with these, the pupils' gender also has an impact on their academic success (Karthigeyan & Nirmala, 2012). Reading carefully through studies on the effect of anxiety on students' academic performance indicated that academic anxiety adversely affects students' academic performance.

Methodology

Respondents

The researcher used a convenience sampling technique, a non-probability sampling technique in which units are chosen for participation in a sample because they are closest to the researchers due to accessibility to the research site and their willingness to participate in the study.

Respondents were recruited from a private school in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. Out of 167 who were given the e-survey, a total of 120 (71.86%) responses were gathered from students while 35 (20.96%) from parents. The sample consisted of 58 male students (48.3%) and 62 female students (51.7%). The mean age of the sample (student-respondents) was 16.45 years (SD = 0.62 years).

Instruments

Academic Anxiety Questionnaire (AAQ). The instrument used to measure the students' academic anxiety is a researcher-made questionnaire whose content validity has been established through a systematic process. The AAQ was subjected to content validation participated by a panel of experts to evaluate each item. The Content Validity Index (I-CVI) of each item was evaluated using a tabulation form where the experts assessed the degree of relevance and the degree of clarity of each item to the measured domain. Those items with an I-CVI value below .70 were eliminated. Consequently, five (5) items from the academic anxiety questionnaire were removed, leaving only twenty (20). Items that were of the given situations in relation to their parenting style.

Recommendations by the experts were revised accordingly. A pilot study was conducted through a Google Form to assess the reliability of the instruments. The AAQ has demonstrated excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.93$) in non-clinical samples ($n=35$) which was assessed through Cronbach's Alpha (coefficient alpha). In terms of stability (test-retest) reliability coefficient, AAQ has demonstrated acceptable reliability at $r = 0.80$ with an interval period of one (1) month. Respondents were asked to indicate the extent they agree or disagree with each of the given statements using a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" (1) to "Strongly Agree" (7). Score in each instrument was calculated by adding together all participant's ratings across the total number of items.

The Parenting Style test created by Robinson et al. (1995) was adopted, modified and used by the researcher to identify the parenting style that the parent-respondent employs. The three (3) scales include autocratic, democratic, and permissive parenting styles. The test uses a 5-point Likert scale from "5 – Always" to "1 – Never" where respondents were asked to indicate how often they attribute each statement.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the data collection, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the school principal of the target institution. The letter covered the study's nature, goal, risks, privacy concerns, methodology, and possible benefits for the institution. Upon approval of the school, the researcher obtained informed consent and disseminated a Google Form consisting of the demographic profile together with the questionnaires used to gather the data. It was also stipulated in the guidelines that respondents' participation in the study is completely voluntary, and they could decide not to participate. The confidentiality and privacy of the respondents' data were guaranteed as well. The e-survey link was sent to the students' Facebook Messenger groups with the assistance of the respective student leaders. The data collection period was completed in two (2) weeks.

Results

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the students in terms of their level of academic anxiety?

Table 1. Sociodemographic profile of the students (n = 120)

Demographic Variables		Low		Moderate		High		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Gender	Male	5	4.17	47	39.17	6	5	58	48.33
	Female	1	0.83	44	36.67	17	14.17	62	51.67
	Total	6	5	91	75.83	23	19.17	120	100
Age (years)	16	3	2.5	56	46.67	14	11.67	73	60.83
	17	3	2.5	30	25	8	6.67	41	34.17
	18	0	0	4	3.33	1	0.83	5	4.17
	19	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	1	0.83
	Total	6	5	91	75.83	23	19.17	120	100
Parental Status	Living with both parents	2	1.67	62	51.67	15	12.50	79	65.83
	Living with guardians	2	1.67	14	11.67	2	1.67	18	15
	Living with mother	2	1.67	12	10.00	5	4.17	19	15.83
	Living with father	0	0	3	2.50	1	0.83	4	3.33
	Total	6	5	91	75.83	23	19.17	120	100

Table 1 illustrates the sociodemographic profile of the respondents according to the level of academic anxiety. In summary, majority or 75.83% ($f = 91$) of the respondents scored moderate, 19.17% ($f = 23$) scored high, and only 5% ($f = 6$) scored low in terms of academic anxiety. In terms of gender, 51.67% ($f = 62$) are female, while 48.33% ($f = 58$) are male. In terms of age, 60.83% ($f = 73$) are 16 years old, 34.17% ($f = 41$) are 17 years old, 4.17% ($f = 5$) are 18 years old, and only 0.83% ($f = 1$) is 19 years old. In terms of family type, majority of the respondents live both parents, representing 65.83% ($f = 79$) of the total sample. Those who live with a guardian/s represent 15% ($f = 18$), while those live with their mother or father only represent 15.83% ($f = 19$) and 3.33% ($f = 4$), respectively.

2. What is the socio-demographic profile of the guardians in terms of their parenting styles?

Table 2. Sociodemographic of the parents / guardians in terms of parenting styles (n = 35)

Demographic Variables		Democratic		Autocratic		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
Age Group	36 to 40 years old	4	11.43	0	0	4	11.43
	41 years old and above	28	80	3	8.57	31	88.57
	Total	32	91.43	3	8.57	35	100
Civil Status	Married	28	80	3	8.57	31	88.57
	Single parent	3	8.57	0	0	3	8.57
	Living with a partner	1	2.86	0	0	1	2.86
	Total	6	5	91	75.83	120	100
Average Monthly Income	10,000-below	2	5.71	0	0	2	5.71
	10,001-20,000	3	8.57	0	0	3	8.57
	20,001-30,000	1	2.86	1	2.86	2	5.72
	30,001-40,000	7	20	0	0	7	20
	40,001-above	19	54.29	2	5.71	21	60
	Total	6	5	91	75.83	120	100

Table 2 illustrates the sociodemographic profile of the parents or guardians according to their parenting styles. In summary, majority or 91.43% (f = 32) of the respondents employ a democratic parenting styles, while only 8.57% (f = 3) employ an autocratic parenting styles. None of the respondents employ a permissive parenting style. In terms of age, 88.57% (f = 31) are 41 years old and above, while only 11.43% (f = 4) fall within the age-range of 36 to 40 years old. Moreover, in terms of civil status, 88.57% (f = 31) are married, 8.57% (f = 3) are single, while 2.86% (f = 1) is living with a partner. Lastly, in terms of average monthly income, 60% (f = 21) of the parents / guardians earn 40,001 pesos and above, 20% (f = 7) earn 30,001 to 40,000 pesos, while the remaining 20% (f = 7) earn 10,000 to 30,000 pesos in a month.

3.1. Is there a significant difference between the students' academic anxiety in terms of gender?

Table 3. Anxiety level of the respondents in terms of gender (t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances)

Variable	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Gender	0.00034	Significant at 0.05 level of significance	Reject the null hypothesis

Table 3 shows that the p-value 0.00034 is statistically significant at .05 level, which shows that the female respondents' level of anxiety is significantly higher than male respondents' level of anxiety. This means that there is a significant difference between the respondents' level of anxiety when grouped according to gender. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected.

3.2 Is there a significant difference between the students' academic anxiety in terms of family structure?

Table 4. Academic anxiety of the respondents in terms of family structure (One Way Analysis of Variance)

Variables	F-Value	P value	Findings	Decision
Family Structure & Academic Anxiety	0.35	0.70	Not significant at 0.05 level of significance	Failed to reject the null hypothesis

Table 4 shows that the p-value 0.70 is not statistically significant at .05 level, which shows that students' family structure has no significant effect towards their academic anxiety. Therefore, the null hypothesis failed to reject.

4. Do parenting styles significantly affect students' academic performance?

Table 5. Parenting styles towards academic performance (t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances)

Variable	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Parenting Styles	0.48	Not significant at 0.05 level of significance	Failed to reject the null hypothesis

A close perusal of Table 5 shows that the level of the respondents' academic performance is not affected by whether their parent's parenting style is either autocratic or democratic. This means that there is no significant difference in terms of academic performance between respondents whose parent's parenting styles are autocratic and democratic. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

5. Does students' academic anxiety significantly affect their academic performance?

Table 6. Academic anxiety towards academic performance (t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances)

Variable	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Academic Anxiety	0.0043	Significant at 0.05 level of significance	Reject the null hypothesis

Table 6 shows that the p-value 0.0043 is statistically significant at .05 level, which shows that the students with low levels of academic anxiety perform better academically than those who have moderate to high level of academic anxiety. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Discussion

The findings of the current study revealed a negative relationship between parenting practices and the academic achievement of grade 11 students in Statefields School. The results of this study support those of Rivers et al. (2012) and of Masud et al. (2016), who found no proof of a relationship between parenting practices and academic achievement. The lack of relevance of the association between parenting styles and accomplishment may be explained by other individual factors that either weaken or increase the relation between parenting styles and academic achievement (Gonzalez et al., 2002).

Another reason for this shaky connection is the fact that as people grow older, the importance of parenting and parental power rapidly decrease, and parents have no more control over their children's education. In actuality, the connections between parenting styles and academic achievement vary between countries based on socioeconomic level, ethnicity, and race (Spera, 2005). There may also be a moderating effect of specific human characteristics on the association between parental behaviors and academic success.

However, there was a discernible difference between male and female students' levels of academic anxiety. It is consistent with the study of MacKinaw-Koons and Vasey (2000) to reach this conclusion. Anxiety is more prevalent in girls than in boys, according to research on children. Additionally, it is possible that social variables like gender roles would be important. Since it represents one of the best remedies, males could feel more socially obligated than women to deal with problems (Hosseini & Khazali, 2013). It is probable that cultural and psychological variables are at play because women have shown to be more sensitive to physiological stress than men (Olff et al., 2007).

Recommendations

Grade 11 students from Statefields School participated in this research study. It is advised that the same study, specifically one on parenting practices, be carried out with more participants. The validity of quantitative research methods may one day also be examined using qualitative research techniques. The results of this study have consequences for educators and other professionals who work with senior high school students who are anxious about their academic performance. Teachers may use a variety of strategies to effectively handle the academic anxiety among pupils, particularly females.

Exam preparation, social support seeking training, relaxation training, and confidence building among the students are a few examples of these methods and strategies. Future research should examine the interactions between teachers and students as well as whether their activities encourage the psychological development of the students. The academic performance of students can be enhanced with this technique. Another benefit of longitudinal study may be the capacity to monitor changes in students' perceptions of their parents' parenting styles and practices in time.

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